

DIGITAL INNOVATIONS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation. The update technology usage and its changes come and give positive effects to us including the teaching and learning process in school practices. It enjoys, motivates, and facilitates the students in learning English. This article aimed at analyzing the English teachers' views on the use of the digital tools in the classroom practices and the challenges in order to face the digital teaching. The results indicated that English teachers agree and strongly agree that digital technology helps the teachers to create interesting atmosphere and technology gives positive effects to the English teaching.

Key words: digital, technology, network, social interactions, materials

Technology gives a chance to the teacher to apply the digital tools into teaching and language learning process. It facilitates and supports the educational field to face the digital teaching. In the digital era, therefore, there is a need to explore the significance of the digital age not just in terms of preparing the learners for an uncertain future, but in building their confident, safe, character as the users of digital technologies now. In the term of internet, technology as ideal tool for language teaching and learning that supports a learner-centred and functional approach to knowledge (Koua, 2013). (Richards & Smith, 2002) stated that computer in language learning is an activity which is parallel learning through other media. It uses the facilities of the computer (e.g. using the computer to present a reading text). Furthermore, (Kiliçkaya & Seferoglu, 2013) indicated that computer technology could improve the students' language skills. It's true that technology gives effect to the teaching and learning process. (Zhytska S.A., 2012) proposed that technology had positive effect on the experiential learning, motivation, enhancing student achievement, authentic materials for learning, greater interaction, individualization, independence from a single source of information, and global understanding. Furthermore, (Sung et al., 2016);(Cong-Lem, 2018) found that technology and web devices gave effect to the students' learning and oral performance. Meanwhile, (Han, 2008) mentioned that computer can promote learning interaction between learners and teachers and it can help classroom teaching with a variety of materials and approaches. (Rahimi & Yadollahi, 2011) investigated the level of ICT in teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) and it can be concluded that digital portable devices were used more than computer or network applications/tools in English classroom and teachers almost provided the technology in teaching oral skills. Furthermore, (Alm, 2016) mentioned that blogging made a special bond between L2 learners which allowed them to see each other as people rather than students. The use of mobile devices among students outside classroom are not something new. (Wu, 2018) mentioned that they need more guidance in order to facilitate the development of their language skills. Thus, students must be monitored and supported by their teachers to use the powerful tools for learning right now. The last, (Parvin & Salam, 2018) found that the use of audio-visual content has positive impact in improving and encouraging interactive language classes Some studies showed that technology significantly improve the learners' language skills. The first, (Nachoua, 2012) found that computer assisted language learning is a motivating method and computers are beneficial tools to be used in foreign language classes in order to improve students' listening skill. The second, (Khoshshima & Khazayi, 2017) mentioned that chatting in cyberspaces (telegram) as one of CALL based activities promote the 20 high school students' speaking ability. The next, (Omar, 2014) found that computer-based concept maps facilitate in improving the students' reading comprehension. The last, (Pirasteh, 2014) stated that using email was effective to teach large number of the structure points. The general research findings that showed the technology provided the capacity to afford opportunities for supporting a powerful teaching and learning atmospheres (Hermans et al., 2008) and can impact on students' learning (Concannon et al., 2005), motivation building (Mahdizadeh et al., 2008), critical thinking building (Lim et al., 2003) , and the autonomy (Claudia et al., 2004) (Baytak et al., 2011) carried out the role of technology in language learning. They found out that learners' learning was improved by integrating technology into the classroom and the use of technology increases learners' motivation, social interactions, learning and engagement. Technology in school makes learning enjoyable, interesting, interactive and helps them learn more. That is why the English teachers should be familiar with the technology tools in English teaching. This research investigated English teachers' views on the use of the digital tools in the classroom practices and the challenges in order to face the digital teaching. The participants' general digital technology using were laptop, computer, speaker, MS PowerPoint, mobile

phone, and the website. The results seem similar to the results of previous research done by (Yordming, 2017), the most common uses of digital tools are the Internet, speaker, computer, and mobile phone. It indicated that the English teachers were familiar with the digital media and tools. In this research, many of the English teachers provided the video as the digital media in teaching and learning process. In the digital age, the teacher has to know where to find relevant information, how to solve problems and what to keep up learning. (Amirsheibani & Iraj, 2014) found that language teachers gave positive attitude on the of computer technology in teaching Moreover. (Anggeraini et al., 2019) found that the EFL teachers had intermediate digital literacy level. General speaking, a teacher has to improve digital technology competences teaching methods and develop professional learning continually along with new developments and to comprehend that change is flow so fast and must accept and prepare for growth. One thing that can be done is learning from networks related to professional developments or personal interests to build knowledge get information and use the technology efficiently in the teaching process. The English teacher can develop professional deal with the technology used the classroom by downloading video teaching tutorial from You Tube and then practice it the classroom. The teacher can learn many useful things from You Tube such as how to make movie maker so that the teacher can create his/her own movie maker as the media in the teaching. This practice is one of practices based learning for professional development for English teachers. They can practice from the native speakers without meeting face to face. It can be the sources for the teacher whom taught in the rural area (in this case, lack of electricity facilities and no internet accesses). (Sung et al., 2016) indicated that the technology is not generally applied in the state schools of the south region of Ecuador. Besides that, the teacher can learn how to operate the online learning application and tools to support the teaching and learning in the digital age. In that case, the teacher should be able to use update and useful application and learning tools in digital age for example online writing applications and tools. In line with (Ozturk, 2013) mentioned about the teachers should re-evaluate their teaching and make best use of potential aids to face the digital teaching. It's true that teachers must digitally literate in order to reach the beneficial and effectiveness of digital teaching. In order to face the digital age teaching, the teachers should participate actively in such kind of professional developments such as seminar, training, workshop that deal with teaching English and technology. By joining such kinds program, the English teachers can upgrade and enlarge their knowledge and skills. The English teachers can also report their research to be presented in the seminar and write article to be published in the academic journal. By attending such kinds of training and seminar, and workshop as the participant or presenter, the English teachers can get the latest information about English teaching nowadays and the important thing is then they can share the result of it with partners.

Conclusion & recommendation In this digital teaching era, the English teacher believed that digital technology gives positive effect to the English teaching, it helps the English teachers to create interesting atmosphere in teaching and learning process, and the digital tools facilitate the teachers in applying digital teaching. Some challenges for teachers in the digital age are: a teacher has to improve teaching methods and develop professional learning continually along with new developments and to comprehend that change is flow so fast and must accept and prepare for growth of technology. In this case, the teacher only focused on the technology used in teaching and learning process (LCD, PPT, video, e-book) but also have technical competence to use various computer applications for educational purposes and be aware of applications that can be suitable for teaching and learning process. The researcher recommends for the other researchers to focus on the teachers` digital competences development to face the teachers` challenges in the digital teaching.

References

1. Alm, A. (2016). Creating willingness to communicate through L2 blogging. In Call-Ej (Vol. 17, Issue 1). Amirsheibani, M., & Iraj, M. (2014). CALL and Teaching Writing: Language Teachers' Attitude, an Iranian Survey. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 98, 258–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.03.415>
2. Anggeraini, Y., Abdurrachman, F., Mujiyanto, J., & Bharati, D. A. L. (2019). The teachers` perceptions on digital literacy competences in EFL classroom. *Asian EFL Journal*, 24(4.1), 5–12.
3. Baytak, A., Tarman, B., & Ayas, C. (2011). Experiencing technology integration in Education. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 3(2), 139–151.
4. Claudia, M., Steil, A. V., & Todesco, J. L. (2004). Factors influencing the adoption of the Internet as a teaching tool at foreign language schools. *Computers and Education*, 42(4), 353–374.
5. Concannon, F., Flynn, A., & Campbell, M. (2005). What campus-based students think about the quality and benefits of e-learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 36(3), 501–512. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2005.00482.x>
6. Cong-Lem, N. (2018). Web-Based Language Learning (WBLL) for enhancing L2 speaking performance: A review. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 9(4), 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.all.v.9n.4p.143>